

Data-Driven Process Optimization in Forming

Wolfram Volk^{1,*}, Christoph Hartmann¹, Lorenz Maier¹

¹Technical University of Munich, Chair of Metal Forming and Casting
Walther-Meissner-Strasse 4, 85748 Garching near Munich Germany

* Corresponding author.

© 2024 The Authors. Published by TU Wien, Institut für Fertigungstechnik und Photonische Technologien.
Peer-review under responsibility of the scientific committee of the 6th Wiener Produktionstechnik Kongress
(WPK 2024)

Keywords: metal forming, process optimization, data-driven models

1 Extended Abstract

Efforts towards interconnected and intelligent production are being promoted at national level in various initiatives, be it 'Industry 4.0' in Germany, 'Society 5.0' in Japan, 'Smart Manufacturing' in the US, 'Industry of the Future' in France, 'Made in China 2025' in China or 'Intelligent Factory' in Italy [1].

An essential component of all these endeavors is the data collected, for example from product design and process development, but especially from ongoing production. This database initially paints an incomplete and disruptive picture of reality in digital form. By curating and statistically analyzing the data, linking it with suitable models makes it possible to derive causal relationships that ultimately lead to decisions and actions. In this context, the term digital twins is used, which are utilized for a variety of tasks. Data-driven approaches are increasingly being used to build models that underlie digital twins, although there are still cross-domain and domain-specific challenges, particularly in the production context. The following aspects are typically major challenges, especially in metal forming [2]:

- Only small (or no) data available in early stages
- Different and incompatible data formats
- No possibilities for data reduction
- Closed-loop interaction between the virtual and real world

This contribution examines approaches and concepts that address the above-mentioned challenges from the perspective of metal forming. However, the proposed solution approaches might be also relevant for other manufacturing techniques, as pointed out in final paragraph.

Central to this is a reverse-engineering algorithm that reconstructs and transforms the geometric data into B-spline surfaces regardless of their origin, i.e. it enables, for example, discrete measurement data, simulation results and analytical design to be mapped in a compatible format [3]. In addition, this format of description enables enormous data reduction, which results in reduced memory requirements and faster data processing. Virtual data from simulations is used to enrich the measurement data or to be able to work at an early stage, for example to design robust and redundant sensor concepts for processes. This type of sensor concept design makes it possible to adapt the underlying simulation model through feedback in a standardized and efficient data format with real data acquisition in production operations [2].

To ensure the best possible quality of the numerical simulation data to be used in this way, a crucial step is its validation. For sheet metal forming this is especially relevant for the material description. The MUC-test is an experimental setup and evaluation routine for the rapid assessment of material models for sheet metal forming [4].

In addition to metal forming, this methodology can be adapted to other manufacturing techniques and even process chains. For example, in series production of additive manufacturing, geometric deviation compensation methods from forming technology [5] could be successfully applied and enabled individualized process control from job to job [6]. In particular, the model-based differentiation between stochastic and deterministic deviations was the focus of interest.

2 References

- [1] Semeraro C, Lezoche M, Panetto H, Dassisti M (2021) Digital twin paradigm: a systematic literature review. *Computers in Industry* 130:103469.
- [2] Maier L, Ünver B, Volk W, Hartmann C (2024) Simulation-based data reduction and data processing for sheet metal forming in the hybrid twin framework. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*. Online First.
- [3] Maier L, Hartmann C, Volk W (2021) Parameterized data handling for forming tool tryout: reverse engineering, data consolidation and springback compensation. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* 1157(1):12035.
- [4] Eder M, Gruber M, Volk W (2022) Validation of material models for sheet metals using new test equipment. *International Journal of Material Forming* 15(5):64.
- [5] Hartmann C, Eder M, Opritescu D, Maier D, Santaella M, Volk W (2018) Geometrical compensation of deterministic deviations for part finishing in bulk forming. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology* 261:140-148.
- [6] Lechner P, Hartmann C, Wolf D, Habiba A (2023) Deviation compensation in LPBF series production via statistical predeformation and structural pattern analysis. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing* 35:2645-2652.